

A NEW APPROACH TO DECISION-MAKING IN CRISIS SITUATIONS

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Abstract: *The problem of making a decision to choose an adequate warehouse in conditions of lack of time, then of goods in the required assortment and quantities at the target destinations, as well as the conditions in which the aforementioned takes place, can be strategic for any organization. There are many criteria that are crucial for choosing the warehouse itself, and they are often opposed to each other. The intensities of the criteria's influence on decision-making are also different. The emphasis in this paper is on defining a multitude of criteria and their causal effects on the decision-making process. This paper offers a proposal for the application of a new multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) model of a unit of the Serbian Armed Forces in the selection of an adequate warehouse for filling with adequate goods the centers for the reception of infected persons that were urgently formed during the Covid-19 crisis. For the above, well-known tools to help decision makers were used; in this case the combined method of AHP and DEMATEL.*

Keywords: *Criteria, warehouse, MCDM, AHP and DEMATEL.*